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RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>High Energy Proton (HEP) testing for the Reliability of Modern Microelectronics in Space Environments (ROMMSE)</i>
Project TA identifier	TA11-356
General application	<i>Reliability, nano-electronics, terrestrial, space, radiation environments</i>
Type of test	SEE
Group leader, Institute	<i>Keith Ryden, University of Surrey Space Centre</i>
Co-authors, Institutes	<i>Matthew Barker, University of Surrey Space Centre</i>
Date(s) of the experiment	12 March 2025
Facility	PARTREC
Amount of access granted	8 h

Objectives of the experiments

Trials have been carried out to determine the SEE characteristics of modern planar SRAMs within a number of environments i.e.

1. Neutron 2.5 MeV, 14 MeV and an accelerated atmospheric spectra at ISIS within Harwell, UK.
2. Proton 2.5 MeV and 14 MeV at CNA, Seville, Spain.

A final data set of High Energy Protons (HEP) is required to complete the analysis for a PhD: Reliability of Modern Microelectronics in Space Environments with the University of Surrey Space Centre.

The objectives of the HEP trial were:

- Carry out Single Event Effects (SEE) tests for 4 different SRAM types focussing upon Single Event Upset (SEU) and observation of Single Event Latch-up (SEL) (including micro-latch) phenomena.
- There should be a sufficient number of tests to reduce statistical uncertainty.
- SEE tests should ensure that the Total Ionising Dose (TID) does not exceed 50 krad (Si).
- SEE tests should be long enough to monitor in real time and record the quiescent current of the SRAMs for micro-SEL behaviour.
- Proton energies shall be carried out at 200 MeV with excursions to other HEP energies if time is available.
- Monitor thermal characteristics of DUTs during irradiation.

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Experiment test report

Figure 1: Set-up of a SEE SRAM test using HEP at PARTREC.

Three 3.3V SRAMs were tested at the maximum energy of 186 MeV in both STATIC and DYNAMIC modes. The results from these tests are presented within Table 1. For Boards Numbers starting with 1 = CY62137FV30LL-45ZSXA, 2 = IS61WV25616BLS-25TLI, 4 = IS61WV204816BLL-10TLI. Several SRAMs were latched at a high flux/fluence ($5E7 \text{ pcm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ for ~12 minutes) and therefore the flux and duration was reduced ($1E7 \text{ pcm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ for ~5 minutes) although SELs were still observed. The Cypress SRAMs exhibited similar micro-latch behaviours that had been observed with both neutrons and protons ≥ 14 MeV which increased the quiescent current as well as generating 'bursts' of upsets. Example data sets are presented within Figure 2 and Figure 3. The SRAMs also had a significant Multiple Bit Upset (MBU) count. Of note was bursts of errors observed within the IS61WV25616BLS-25TLI. These had not shown burst effects from other irradiation sources (2.5 & 14 MeV protons and neutrons and an accelerated atmospheric neutron spectra). There was not an observed change in current or increase in MBU count for this SRAM type which would indicate different mechanisms between the two. The SEU Cross Section (CS) values align with historic testing of SRAMs from the year 2000.

Experiment Number	Board Number	Mode: DYNAMIC / STATIC	SEU Count	MBU Count	Fluence (p cm^{-2})	SEU CS ($\text{cm}^2 \text{ bit}^{-1}$)	SEE Type
1	24C	S	N/A	N/A	3.00E+10	N/A	SEL
1	27Bi	D	566	0	1.37E+10	9.83E-15	SEU & SEL
1	27Bii	D	7,283	0	1.44E+10	1.20E-13	SEU & SEL

3	25	S	484	0	3.00E+09	3.85E-14	SEU
3	26i	D	158	0	2.48E+09	1.52E-14	SEU & SEL
3	26ii	D	7,351	0	2.60E+09	6.73E-13	SEU & SEL
4	14	S	22,624	18885	2.32E+09	N/A	SEFI
4	15	D	3835	285	2.32E+09	6.10E-13	SEU
5	12i	S	2839	571	3.55E+08	3.81E-12	SEU
5	12ii	S	10,098	1701	2.40E+09	2.01E-12	SEU
5	16	D	4193	1173	2.40E+09	8.33E-13	SEU
6	47	D	114	0	2.40E+09	5.66E-15	SEU
7	47	S	271	0	2.34E+09	1.38E-14	SEU

Table 1: Results from HEP trial at PARTREC.

Figure 2: Upset instantaneous and cumulative count from a HEP test with a CY62137FV30LL-45ZSXA SRAM.

Figure 3: Supply current and cumulative count from a HEP test with a CY62137FV30LL-45ZSXA SRAM.

Comparing the HEP data with that from an accelerated atmospheric neutron spectra (Chiplr) shows a variety of ratios. For the CY62137FV30LL-45ZSXA SRAM the proton:neutron CS ratio varies between 3.3 to 8.7. This is a highly variable SRAM that is sensitive to bursts of upsets from micro-latches. For the IS61WV25616BLS-25TLI, the ratio is between 0.26 to 14.23. This variability is due to the bursts of upsets observed during the HEP trial. For the IS61WV204816BLL-10TLI which has been stable at energies ≥ 14 MeV the ratio is stable between 0.29 to 0.55.

Thermal imaging was used (see Figure 4) to capture the increased temperature generated from micro-latches within the CY62137FV30LL-45ZSXA SRAM. Due to a short amount of time available only one set of measurements could be taken but did demonstrate an increase of die temperature by ~ 9 °C. Higher values have been observed by other experimenters but for a development test-SRAM. These values are being analysed for the impact on the SRAM's lifetime reliability.

Figure 4: Thermal image from a HEP test with a CY62137FV30LL-45ZSXA SRAM.

The SEU CS values have been used from the HEP trial with those from the other trials to generate Weibull curves and apply them into the Models for Atmospheric Ionising Radiation Effects (MAIRE) tool. Upset values have been determined for a variety of locations and environmental conditions (benign and Ground Level Enhancement (GLE) 05). For the extreme environment at 21 km Above Sea Level (ASL) there is a significant risk to electronics particularly over polar regions which would see significant upsets >14 upsets per Mb per hour (see Figure 5). This should be a concern for modern aircraft using the North Pole flight path as well as for future supersonic aircraft. There is a similar risk of micro-latches occurring reducing a components lifetime reliability.

Figure 5: Upset rates for a CY62137FV30LL-45ZSXA SRAM at 21 km Above Sea Level during GLE-05.

The primary objectives of the experiment were met however there was limited beam time provided from RADNEXT. Therefore; one SRAM type could not be tested, there were fewer tests on SRAMs which reduced the data set and the thermal imaging was not as comprehensive as intended.

The data is being used to support a University of Surrey PhD: Reliability of nano-electronics within terrestrial and space radiation environments.

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	X
Data for Thesis	X
Follow-up experiment at same facility	
Follow-up experiment at another facility	
Other	

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

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